

THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Ilkhamova Yodgorakhon Saidakhmedovna

professor, Head of the Department of Electronic Commerce and Digital Economy, at the Tashkent Institute of Finance.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543146>

The Digital Economy is an economic activity based on digital technologies and innovative solutions, which are the basic production factors and provide higher business efficiency. The field of the digital economy mainly includes companies in the financial sector, insurance, commerce (including e-commerce). The Digital Economy also includes activities related to the provision of online services, with electronic payments, crowdfunding, blockchain and cryptocurrencies.

The characteristic features of the digital economy are:

- ❖ concentration of economic activity on platforms. Platforms are called digital software and hardware systems with certain functionality that meet the needs of users and producers of goods and services, as well as supporting the possibility of direct interaction between them. Thanks to this, platforms significantly improve the quality of cooperation between the parties and contribute to the creation of new products and solutions. Examples of the most famous platforms are Uber and Airbnb;
- ❖ development of personalized service models - the production of goods and the provision of services meets the requirements and needs not of the average user, but of each specific client, which has become real thanks to the active use of Big Data technologies and targeted marketing;
- ❖ operational interaction between producers and consumers, which allows to exclude intermediaries from the chain of relations;
- ❖ the spread of the sharing economy - the replacement of ownership of goods and services by barter and rent, as well as payment for the provision of information. Paying for information is a trend that has not yet gained much popularity, but suggests the imminent appearance of “connected spy goods”, the cost of which will be much lower than that of analogues. The difference in cost will be compensated by the manufacturer itself, which, using these products, will collect user data and monetize information through targeted marketing, provision of additional personalized services (based on the collected information) or direct sale of information;
- ❖ increasing role of individual participants. In the digital economy, along with the traditional models of interaction B2B, B2C, B2G, C2B and C2C schemes appear. An example of a C2B relationship is the work of freelancers doing

contracted tasks outsourced. The type of C2C interactions is, for example, CrowdFunding startups (American kickstarter.com, Russian planeta.ru).

The development of the digital economy contributes to the growth of labor productivity, the emergence of new jobs, an increase in the number of competitive companies and a reduction in production costs.

In relation to the digital economy, the figure is understood as a signal that transmits a number or a control impulse that reaches each economic agent (supplier, consumer, intermediary, etc.), which creates qualitatively new opportunities for the automatic management of production and logistics processes within the enterprise and the whole economy of the country. The maximum level of efficiency is achieved when all transactions are carried out automatically along the entire chain (end-to-end technologies), without human intervention, and transaction costs are reduced to almost zero. End-to-end digital technologies include:

- big data (Big Data);
- artificial intelligence (AI) and neurotechnologies;
- distributed registry systems (blockchain);
- quantum technologies;
- Industrial Internet (IoT);
- robotics and sensor components;
- wireless communication technologies (introduction of 5G networks);
- technologies of virtual and augmented reality, which are becoming more and more available for mass use.

Digital transformation, as another key component of the concept of "digital economy", involves not so much the introduction of digital technologies as a change in business processes and management institutions so that an enterprise, organization or government body can take advantage of new technologies. Digital transformation is implemented by transforming the existing business processes in the enterprise in the direction of their "seamlessness" and following the principle of the concept of intelligent management, due to which there is a transition from planning based on information processing through ICT, when information is presented as a representation of a numerical value, to direct automatic control based on an end-to-end digital signal.

At the same time, if traditional information technologies are aimed more at analyzing the state of the enterprise and solving individual problems, formal, controlled and under centralized control, then the use of digital technologies is

more focused on solving user problems, which are mainly informal in nature and are aimed on the interests and convenience of customers.

At the enterprise level, digital transformation means moving from a traditional IT service (task-focused, formalized, controlled, managed, and costly) to a human-centered, open systems world (informal, spontaneous, empathic, and affordable). As a result, information and digital technologies cease to be internal resources and assets of an enterprise and turn into factors in the formation and development of new markets for goods and services based on new business models.

Thus, the transformation of business models under the influence of digital technologies and the formation of digital ecosystems is objectively due to the ever-increasing complexity of the economy and, as a result, the growth of information activities to ensure the interaction of all links in the production of goods and services and the increasing consideration of individual consumer needs.

The digital economy is formed on the basis of digitalization and has its own specifics, determined by the nature of creating added value by increasing and systematizing digital content (object of labor), increasing the intellectualization of its processing algorithms automatically (without human intervention and with increasing consideration of the nonlinearity of real processes) and depending on environmental signals. One of the key characteristics of the digital economy is the speed of changes in the production of goods and services, in applied business models and management.

Quantitative changes in business models under the influence of cheaper and more widespread use of digital devices have led to the emergence of new digital technologies that are the basis of a modern economy based on predominantly horizontal interactions (self-organization and singularity), innovative entrepreneurship (self-development), information engineering (self-improvement) and auto-formalization (auto-structuring) of economic processes.

References:

1. Abdullaev N.K. (2022). Digital economy: concepts and directions of development. Science and Innovations, No. 1, pp. 148-155.
2. Bukht R., Hicks R. Definition, concept and measurement of the digital economy // <https://iorj.hse.ru/data/>
3. Digital technologies // <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki>.

